

Evolution of brain MRI signals after decompressive craniectomy for experimental intracerebral hemorrhage

Shashank Shekhar (MBBS, MSc)^{1,2,3*}, Ivan Marinkovic (MD)^{1,2}, Aysan Durukan (MD)^{1,2}, Miia Pitkonen (MSc)², Daniel Strbian (MD, PhD)^{1,2}, Usama Abo Ramadan (PhD)², Turgut Tatlisumak (MD, PhD)^{1,2}

* Corresponding Author

¹Department of Neurology, Helsinki University Central Hospital, Helsinki, Finland

²Experimental MRI Laboratory, Biomedicum Helsinki, Helsinki, Finland

³Institute of Clinical medicine, University of Turku, Finland

Correspondence to: Shashank Shekhar

Email: shashank.shekhar@utu.fi

Purpose: Decompressive Craniectomy (DC) improves outcomes after experimental Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) in rats. We tested whether DC was associated with changes in magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) signals in the lesioned brain hemisphere.

Materials and Methods: Four groups of rats underwent stereotactically-guided injection of autologous blood into the basal ganglia. Animals were randomly allocated to no decompressive craniectomy (No-DC) or to decompressive craniectomy at 1 hour (1h-DC), 6 hours (6h-DC), or 24 hours (24h-DC). A fifth group without ICH underwent craniectomy only (DC-only). All animals were serially evaluated by MRI at days 0, 3, and 7.

Results: In perihematomal region, relative apparent diffusion coefficient (rADC) and relative T2-Signal intensity (rT2-SI) values increased in all groups from day 0 to day 3 and reduced at day 7. rADC in the cortical region on day 3 was increased in rats with ICH treated with early DC (1 and 6 h) post ICH compared to the No-DC group. There was no corresponding rT2-SI values change, however, slight increases in values were observed with time.

In the No-DC group, no decreases in (rADC) values were observed in the perihematomal ROI.

Conclusions: DC performed at 1 and 6 hours post-ICH induced MRI changes indicative of brain edema both in perihematomal tissue and the cortex. There was no evidence of perihematomal penumbra or secondary ischemic injury in the cortex.

Clinical Relevance: Increased perihematomal and increased cortical rADC values may be predictors of favorable outcome in ICH treated with DC.